

Sustainable Finance – A New Route for Endurable Development

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Abstract

In the era of economic advancement the world is facing serious environmental degradation. The rapid economic development is leading towards major resource depletion and environmental damage which is impossible to be repaired. Thus, there is an urgent call to develop and implement sustainable tools in order to preserve the environment for betterment along with striving for development. In the past days, investors considered returns and risk are the only criterions for considering the investment. But, today there is a need to eye on environmental and societal issues but not just the financial returns. Sustainable finance is one such great tool for the above issues. Sustainable finance is the integration of Environmental, Social and Governmental (ESG) financial service criteria into the business or investment decisions for the long lasting advantages of client base and the society at a large. Sustainable finance acts as a bridge for development of economy with the preservation of natural resources and reducing damage of environmental depletion. Sustainable finance with its rising importance these days provides market participants an option to choose to behave in a more accountable means and carry the optimistic changes in the day to day business. The objective of this paper is to highlight the various concepts related to Sustainable finance as a new way of justifiable development. The study is mainly based on the secondary sources of information and by applying the analytical research it tries to understand the contributions towards sustainable development. The paper briefs about sustainable finance industry and the ways in which it is serving towards sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: Sustainable finance, Environmental, Social and Governmental (ESG).

Introduction

Sustainable development is the critical concern that needs to be addressed across the Globe today. The World Commission on Environment and Development defines sustainability as follows—“meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” Sustainable development is the one which addresses the needs of existing generation without adjusting or depriving the needs of upcoming generations. It also assures the balance of economic growth and care for environment and societal well-being.

The concepts of Sustainable development emerged in 1987 from Brundtland report which raised the issue of negative impacts of economic growth and globalization and also tried to propose reliable suggestions to the harm caused by excessive industrial escalation and mounting population. Sustainability basically stands on three pillars; Economic, Environmental and Social which can also be called as Profits, Planet and People. Sustainability urges the financial organisations to strive for long term development rather than achieving short term turnovers and profits. Sustainability involves various factors to be considered instead of just focusing on financial gains.

Conventionally, investors evaluated their investments only on the basis of risk and returns. But, investing with the objective of protecting environment and society but not concentrating on financial returns only has procured essential importance in the recent past. The one such avenue is provided by Sustainable finance. Sustainable finance is the financial services carried out in any form along with the consideration towards Environment, Society and Government criteria onto the business or investment.

Currently the world is witnessing a global era of exploitation, where the major part of the human lifestyle has changed. Climate is one such aspect. As humans, it is our primary responsibility to act and modify to the margins of our planet. Individuals are switching towards organic food from chemically grown food in order to obtain better health, the same frame of mind needs to be developed while investing.

Financial institutions play a vital role in the society. These corporations assist individuals in satisfying their dreams by providing required financial assistance. The financial assistance provided and dispersed by these institutions will be invested with the objective of earning growth and profit. Thus, it is required to make certain that money invested will be on sustainable platforms which assure common good. This can be certified by the criteria of Sustainable finance.

A monetary market place which contributes in the direction of sustainable development formation of value in terms of Economy, Society and Environment is can be quoted as Sustainable finance. Sustainable finance can also be quoted in the following way. It is the one which ensures and promotes economical efficiency, fruitfulness and competitiveness both in the current and long term scenarios. Meanwhile, it also contributes to the rehabilitation of natural systems and boosting up of cultural diversity and societal comfort.

Objectives of the Study

- To highlight the concepts related to Sustainable finance
- To propose a feasible model for creation of Sustainable finance
- To enhance further research in the field of Sustainable finance

Review of Literature

1. Dr Mellisa Edward, Dr Scott Kelly, Dr Alice Klettner and Dr Paul Brown (2019) have observed that Sustainable Finance is a bunch of financial services which includes activities of investment, insurance, banking, accounting, trading and reporting that crosses the limits of as usual business by assimilating ESG criteria into their activities with the goal of earning long term gain to their clients, stake holders and society as a whole.
2. Giovanni Ferri and Bonnie Annete Acosta (2019) are of the opinion that Sustainable Finance is the key to reach sustainable development by resolving environmental risk through green finance. The authors also highlight about the role of MSEs, Alternative Banking Systems, Microfinance Organizations, Digital market payments, Crowd funding, Impact investing and other tools in the development of Sustainable Finance.

3. Celine Bake (2019) has researched that Sustainable Finance is a tool of upholding enduring economic growth and long term constancy of the financial system through the integration of environmental and social factors in the activities of capital allocation, risk management and other financial processes. The author also states that in order to practice and government and private sectors need to contribute equally.
4. The research of Alapathi Bharath Reddy (2018) has conveyed that Sustainable Finance suffers from various restraints for its effective implementation in India such as lack of stable policies, little profitability in sustainable industries, not having measurement tools in assessing the viability of these businesses and lack of awareness of consumers and investors in green products and investment avenues.
5. The research of David M. Solomon, John E. Waldron, Stephen M. Scherr (2018) has highlighted five critical steps in effective implementation of Sustainable Finance in the organizations namely driving for sustainable growth by rising capital to support sustainable business models, creating financial empowerment to capitalize them, advancing environmental progress by leveraging capital markets to alleviate the impact of negative changes in nature, maintaining a highly dedicated work force who are ambitious to provide value to clients and managing everything conscientiously.

Forms of Sustainable Finance

Sustainable Finance covers huge areas of activities. Some of the major areas of operations are highlighted below,

Sustainable Lending

Sustainable lending refers to a lending on environmental criteria for the planned use of funds. The major objective here is to finance the individuals in their green projects. Some of the areas where sustainable lending can be obtained are,

- Renewable energy
- Green buildings
- Waste management
- Low carbon transportation

Sustainable Investments

Sustainable Investments are often used with term Socially Responsible Investing (SRI). Sustainable investments are essentially investment activities that focus on companies or projects that are committed to the conservation of natural resources, the production and discovery of alternative energy sources, the implementation of clean air and water projects, and/or other environmentally conscious business practices. Sustainable investments may fit under the umbrella of SRI, but is fundamentally much more specific.

Some of the sustainable investments can be quoted as follows,

- Sustainable Mutual Funds
- Sustainable Bonds
- Blue Bonds

Sustainable Insurance

For consumers and business owners committed to “going green”, a wide range of insurance options is now available. Below is a breakdown of some of the innovative, eco-friendly products, services and discounts offered by many insurers. Some of the sustainable insurance products are,

- Hybrid discounts
- Alternative fuel discounts
- Green commercial property insurance policies and endorsement

Model for Creation of Sustainable Finance

Creation of Sustainable Finance in any organization is a tricky task. After careful investigation and detailed literature review below is one such model which highlights the critical areas which has to be strengthened in order to ensure effective implementation of sustainable finance. The following model can be referred as a basic outline for creation of sustainable finance,

Risk identification & Risk Management	Creation of positive thinking	New ways of implementation
Assessment of environmental risk during the major financial decision making	Creating awareness in the minds of the investors about the importance of sustainable development	Finding out novel ways of promoting and implementing of sustainable financial activities and models

Risk Identification and Risk Management

Every financial decision has its own impact on environment. Thus while taking any of them it is necessary to identify the risks associated towards environment and suitable risk management techniques needs to implied in order to ensure sustainability.

Creation of Positive Thinking

It is a known fact that sustainable finance is not of much familiar investment avenue for the investors. Hence, it becomes primary to provide necessary information with regard to the sustainable investment avenues and its impact on the Environment, Society and Government.

New Ways of Implementation

Along with the existing models of sustainable finance, an innovative and creative thinking has to be done in order to convert an idea which is sustainable in to a new product or an avenue for investment.

Sustainable Finance Ecosystem

The following graphical representation shows a conducive Sustainable Finance Ecosystem from which we can expect higher GDP, more employment generation, cleaner environment, enhanced livelihood and secure future.

Sustainable Finance Challenges

Sustainable Finance can be a golden era of innovative investment. But, it has to overcome from challenges. Investors, especially Indian investor’s typical mind set of earning more and more profits may not support towards investment in sustainable finance as returns on the sustainable finance avenues may not yield a high return to them. Riskiness in the Sustainable Finance is yet another challenging factor for its growth. As most of the Indian investors are risk avoiders than risk seekers. Communication and Monitoring of the Sustainable environment project is another challenge. Though Government of India (GOI) has initiated many schemes and programs which enhance the protection of environment and society, not many entrepreneurs and general public are fully aware. Hence providing proper communication for prospective investor is important. Legal Standards has been framed for protecting the investors in terms of safeguarding their money invested.

Conclusion

Drastic developments in the field of science and technology are vast and have resulted in effecting the environment at large. Thus there is a need to concentrate on Sustainable development in order to preserve and grow in the long run. One such tool is sustainable finance. Investors should gain knowledge about innovative avenues in sustainable finance and change their mind sets towards risk and return aspect. Many banks, financial institutions and multi-national companies are now moving towards investments in sustainable projects as one of their long term strategy and corporate social responsibility and in turn creating awareness among the prospective investors about the same.

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